

THE IMPORTANCE OF MEDOTES IN PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

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Annotation: in this scientific article, the methodology of teaching pedagogy is based on the philosophical and special-scientific degrees of the methodology of science. It should be noted that all levels of methodology are interconnected and subordinate to each other, so they form a holistic system.

Keywords: nationality education, educational institution, technical devices, teaching methodology, contemporary science, technique.

Modern and nationalistic education means that only if modern technical devices, tools, appropriate use of educational literature are provided and educated, there will be high spiritual and moral potential and highly qualified people. Another of the important principles of the methodology for teaching Pedagogical Sciences is the intelligibility of information, the consistency and structure of their statement. Basically, intelligibility the volume of information from the educator predicts that the degree of difficulty should be consistent with the age of the learners, the possibility of real learning, individual characteristics. In the process of following the principle, it is necessary that the educational subject does not memorize the section, the timing of the study of questions. As such, the principle of comprehensiveness requires a new concept, the present in the darklarks, the achievements of Science, Technology, the size of terms, the place of the problem being studied in the curriculum, the methods and methods of teaching should be clearly defined by the teacher. Individual characteristics that must be followed during the teaching process include students' interests, level of development, feelings, temperament, character traits, ability, inclinations, marital tarsi. The principle of intelligibility is applied in the manner of interaction with the principle of consistency and systematicity, in which, in the study of issues, a) from known to unknown; B) from simple to complex; C) from clear to uncertain g) from easy to difficult d) from general to private, based on following the rules. To the principle of consistency of Education Y.A.Komensky founded, and then these principles were introduced by the Russian pedagogue K.D.Developed by ushinsky. The experience shows that consistent and system-stated information is consciously assimilated, stored in memory for a long time. It is difficult to assimilate the information stated on the basis of the excerpt. Therefore, if knowledge is expressed on the basis of a particular system of consistency they will be interconnected, and the latter will complement the first. Based on this, the study of knowledge in the direction of a holistic certain consistency, systemality in interdependence carries out the formation of a perfectly improving personality. Consistency and systematicity the exact planning of the entire educational process helps to rationally provide the information of the lessons, knowledge is comprehensively mastered, logical thinking develops. The principle of independence and initiative of creative activity of students in mastering pedagogical data is

like a tree that blooms and gives a lot of dressing, having an important importance in science. If the student creatively assimilates the materials of Pedagogical Sciences and independently replenishes knowledge from additional literature, of course, it will be a person who will take the initiative and work. one of the issues also provided for in the "national program of Personnel Training " is the training of qualified, qualified personnel through the formation of independence, initiative of creative activity in students. Independence fosters creative activity in its direction, creative activity encourages initiative. These are pedagogical phenomena that are interconnected in the form of cause and effect. After all, it is difficult to educate the creative mastery of pedagogical knowledge to be active and enterprising without ensuring independence in the teaching of Pedagogical Sciences, as it cannot be said about the initiative of " creative activity of students in a place that has not achieved real independence." Indeed, the principle of independence is the principle that the period requires socioeconomic bargaining. Because, Independence forms free thinking, creative ability, mental resourcefulness in students.

The principle of optimizing the educational process in the process of teaching pedagogical subjects, belonging to a particular system the concept of "Systemality" is also known in this place pedagogical category refers to the process of teaching the educational discipline, to the general educational process, to the totality. In this regard, the acquired knowledge of Pedagogical Sciences, pedagogy and psychology are recognized as the creation of a process for creating favorable conditions for obtaining the necessary information (knowledge) at the heart of the educational direction. This will be aimed at acquiring theoretical and practical information on the pedagogical aspects of this field, as well as performing activities specific to upbringing, and at carrying out the established tasks in a timely manner. The second aspect is that comparing the subjects of Pedagogical Sciences with each other, realizing the similar, complementary aspects, aims to teach them the importance for the profession they are acquiring. Communicating this to the mind of a harbir student, to the consciousness, are the main tasks of a higher education educator. The principle of choosing additional information in the teaching of Pedagogical Sciences. This principle implies that the content of the sciences should be taken into account, determine whether the new information on the stated topic is in accordance with the requirements of the period, socio-economic development and fill them in accordance with the achievements of Pedagogical Sciences, advanced pedagogical requirements. Such an approach makes it possible to achieve the effectiveness of pedagogical education, enrich the training with new information and accurately convey to students, increase its activity. The choice of additional information in the teaching of pedagogical subjects in terms of universal rules, principles, provides, first of all, information content, and secondly, increases student activity, helps to cultivate the skills of educators and students to work with resources in training, the ability to research. The educational goal increases, new knowledge, skills to work with new resources and acquire additional information are formed in students. Thus analyzed, these submissions help to organize the teaching of Pedagogical Sciences in higher educational institutions on the basis of the requirements of the period, increase the pedagogical literacy of students, develop a sense of pride and pride in the achievements.

In modern conditions, the main tasks of pedagogy are aimed at creating effective pedagogical systems in all directions of the human lifestyle (social, personal, political, etc.). A system (sistema) is a pedagogical phenomenon that is ordered, interconnected and acting; it

is the sum of ordered concepts. A system (sistema) is a solid unit and connection between many elements that are interconnected.

The system of Pedagogical Sciences includes:

1. General pedagogy – studies the Basic Laws of education and upbringing.
2. Age pedagogy-studies the peculiarities of teaching and raising children of different ages. It is divided into preschool pedagogy, school pedagogy, Higher School pedagogy, senior pedagogy (andragogy).
3. Special pedagogy (defectology) is a science that studies the laws, principles, purpose, content, methods and Means and form of teaching and educating children with disabilities in mental, mental, physical development.

This in turn is divided into four directions:

- a) surdopedagogics deals with the education and upbringing of deaf and dumb children.
 - b) tiflopedagogics – deals with the education and upbringing of Blind Children.
 - s) oligofpenopedagogy – deals with the education and upbringing of mentally retarded children.
 - d) speech therapy – deals with the education and upbringing of children whose speech is not well developed.
4. Methodology-studies the laws of teaching a certain educational discipline in the field of pedagogical science. For example, the methodology of languages, the methodology of mathematics, the methodology of educational work, etc.
 5. History of pedagogy-studies the development of pedagogical ideas and upbringing in different historical periods.
 6. Social pedagogy-studies the role and role of pedagogical ideas in the processes of social relations, the problems of directing the individual to social activities.
 7. Comparative pedagogy is an independent field of pedagogy that studies the comparison of the educational and educational system of different countries, the development of Education.
 8. Folk pedagogy is an independent field of pedagogy that studies the essence, content of pedagogical ideas about education and education in the folk oral creativity of various peoples, nationalities and elates.
 9. Pedagogical skills-study the problems of improving, improving the personal and professional skills of future teachers. Modern branches of pedagogy, which have appeared in the process of integration of Sciences in the current period, are also forming and developing.

Pedagogical Axiology-theoretical knowledge of pedagogical innovations, assessment of the degree of assimilation of innovations by the pedagogical public, perception. Pedagogical acmeology is a science that studies the problems of reaching the highest stage of the teacher's professional activity. Pedagogical riskology-studies the characteristics of risk in the process of making the most important decisions in pedagogical situations. Pedagogical qualimetry-studies the measure and criterion of the levels of quality and efficiency that an educator achieves in the process of activity. Neuropedagogy-Studies new scientific programs, effective forms and methods of determining and practical (functional) development of the creative capabilities of the human brain, finding a decision on an active, conscious attitude towards activity in a person, psychological correction of social behavior, diagnosis and prediction of children's mental development, the activities of new types of preschool educational institutions.

Education is such a process of cognition in which students, with the help and guidance of a teacher, apply with scientific knowledge, acquire practical skills and abilities, develop mental and physical forces, form worldviews, spiritual and moral qualities, prepare for life and work. Information is the sum of systematized and generalized cognitive skills and qualifications. In a word, education is the result of upbringing special. All this is realized and taken into action in the pedagogical process. In this sense, the pedagogical process is the process of holistic educational education, the formation of a person who has matured in every possible way with the help of creative activities in the cooperation of those who receive education on the basis of upbringing and education in its integrity.

In order to prepare such a breed as a person who made a worthy contribution to life education, orientation and social progress, the science of "Pedagogy" came to the field. At first, in primitive society, adults were engaged in the fact that they would follow their children with them, teach them such things as collecting the beliefs of nature, hunting together, and later farming. Then the children will be protected from various natural disasters by tribal chiefs and the elderly, the formation of mountain building water foundations for farming, the treatment of diseases, the renewal of their lifestyle, the choice of a Sara of food for living, the vital need to build huts gives the growing younger generation the need to teach the elderly their experiences. The vital need gave rise to the growing young generation the need to teach the elderly their experiences, a necessity that began to be carried out with the elderly in the process of direct labor activities of young people. Thus, one of the important components of pedagogy is upbringing and they were bred by educators who make up young people. These were parents and old people of the tribe in antiquity. They were mainly people who direct young people to fulfill qualities such as the use of the beliefs of nature, the struggle with the whims of nature to perform household chores and the teaching of moral odonb attitude among people. Thus, the pedagogy of wisdom was formed, a complex of knowledge that explains the treatment of nature, reciprocity, the environment surrounding oneself, the treatment of people of the tribe in the framework of morality to Elat. This pedagogy has served a lot in the harmonious implementation of spiritual and moral qualities in children, such as diligence, popularism, hard work.

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